

Characterisation of Oxidation Catalysts—Reaction of Propan-2-ol on a Zn : Cr : Fe Catalyst

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The vapour phase catalytic reactions of propan-2-ol have been investigated on a Zn : Cr : Fe catalyst system in a flow reactor. Both normal dehydrogenation and oxidative dehydrogenation of propan-2-ol take place. The reaction products have been identified and the catalyst activity is found to be decreasing with time of use for both types of reactions.

Addition of oxygen has a beneficial effect on the dehydrogenation activity of the catalyst, but at high partial pressures causes drastic oxidation of the target product first and subsequently the reactant itself. In addition to the surface reaction it is observed that there is also a homogeneous, gas phase reaction giving rise to the same product acetone.

The results support the view that in the mild oxidation, the oxidising species is the oxide ion for the surface reaction and molecular oxygen for the reaction taking place homogeneously in the gas phase.

MOST work to date on vapour phase catalytic oxidation has been carried out with oxygen added to the feed. Bismuth molybdate catalysts are able to oxidize alkenes selectively even in the absence of molecular oxygen^{1,2}. The activity for a highly selective oxidation is maintained for a much shorter time than in the presence of oxygen. The loss in activity is associated with the progressive reduction of the catalyst. In a recent communication the results of a study of catalytic activity and selectivity of various oxidation catalysts for the decomposition of propan-2-ol were reported^{3,4}. It appears that a high level of oxidation of the catalyst must be maintained for good selectivity. Rennard and Kehl⁵ have reported that a Zn:Cr:Fe catalyst system is a good oxidative dehydrogenation catalyst for butene. The present study is an attempt to understand the roles of oxide ions, chemisorbed oxygen and gaseous oxygen for the selective oxidation of propan-2-ol to acetone on a catalyst containing Zn, Cr and Fe.

Experimental

Preparation of catalysts: All the chemicals were Analar grade B.D.H. reagents and were used as received. Because simple precipitation methods often produce ill defined catalysts, the Zn:Cr:Fe catalyst was prepared by the slurry method described by Batist⁶. The following chemicals were used as starting materials. Nitrate was used for iron and chromium and oxide was used for zinc. Fe(OH)₃ and Cr(OH)₃ were obtained by precipitation from nitrate solutions by the slow addition of analar ammonia (B.D.H) keeping the system stirred. A zinc oxide paste made with distilled water was added to the mixture of freshly precipitated, thoroughly washed Fe(OH)₃ and Cr(OH)₃ and allowed to heat for

10 hours on a boiling water bath keeping the total mass stirred vigorously. After reaction the solids were filtered, dried at 110° over night and calcined at 550° for 5 hrs.

Propan-2-ol and acetone (B.D.H., A.R chemicals) found to be chromatographically pure were used without further purification.

Research grade oxygen kindly supplied by I.O.L., Madras, was used directly from the cylinder after passing through gas-towers containing sodalime, fused calcium chloride and concentrated sulphuric acid for the removal of CO₂ and moisture respectively.

Hydrogen and nitrogen were also used directly from cylinders after passing through the above driers. N₂ was found to be inert on the catalyst by comparing its behaviour with He. Carbon dioxide from the cylinder was passed only through fused calcium chloride and con.H₂SO₄ before use. The flow of gases were controlled by needle valves and was maintained constant by using a manostat.

Each run was continued for approximately one hour. Duplicate runs were made at each set of conditions to ensure reproducibility.

Reactions were carried out in a flow type reactor working at atmospheric pressure. The packing of the reactor and the experimental procedure has been described in an earlier paper⁷. Activation was done by passing dry air over the catalyst maintained at 450° for 20 minutes. The liquid products were analysed by gas

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chromatography using a carbowax column at 75° and the gaseous products were analysed using an Orsat's apparatus⁷.

Results and Discussion

Various compositions of ternary oxides of Zn, Cr and Fe catalysts were prepared and tested for the decomposition of propan-2-ol. Both dehydrogenation and dehydration take place except on a catalyst of composition 1:1:1 (of cations) which caused only dehydrogenation to take place.

The catalytic activity of Zn:Cr:Fe (1:1:1 fresh sample) for the dehydrogenation of propan-2-ol decreases with time of reaction. The activity of the catalyst for the formation of acetone is given by the ratio of the number of moles of acetone formed to number of moles of alcohol fed. The decrease in activity with time is shown in fig. 1. When the aged catalyst is regenerated with air the activity was found to be slightly less than that of a fresh catalyst. After the third cycle the activity of the regenerated catalyst was found to have stabilised. Even a stabilised catalyst loses its activity with time of reaction as shown in fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Effect of a) Time at 400°C and b) Temperature on conversion of propan-2-ol.

The catalyst can be regenerated any number of times indicating that the deactivation is reversible and oxidation restores activity. During regeneration, qualitative tests of the exit gas showed that there was no CO_2 , proving that there was no coke formation on the catalyst. Acetone and water are found to be the main products of reaction. Analyses of the gaseous products do not indicate the presence of propylene showing that the water formed is not due to dehydration of propan-

2-ol. The formation of water could have only been due to oxidative dehydrogenation of the alcohol. At 330° the conversion to acetone is 10% and it increases with temperature as shown in Fig. 1.

These observations lead to the following inference :

1) The decomposition of propan-2-ol occurs according to the Mars and Van Krevelen mechanism⁸.

Mars and Van Krevelen considered that the loss of oxygen atoms from the lattice is by the direct interaction with the reducing agent. (2) The reoxidation of the catalyst proceeds rapidly as in Mo-containing catalysts⁹. (3) No coke deposit is formed on the catalyst during the decomposition reaction.

The oxidation of alcohol has been tried at various mole ratios of oxygen and alcohol. Oxygen causes a considerable enhancement in the formation of acetone as compared with the decomposition of alcohol in the presence of N_2 (fig. 2). The products are acetone, water and carbon dioxide. The formation of acetone is maximum at a mole ratio of oxygen to alcohol of 0.2. Attempts to increase the yield of acetone by increasing the partial pressure of oxygen or temperature (fig. 2) caused the activity to pass through a maximum. For a partial pressure of oxygen of 0.2 the activity is maximum at 410°. The necessary conditions for the maximum yield of ketone are the presence of an optimum amount of oxygen in the feed and a moderate temperature of oxidation.

Fig. 2. Effect of a) The variation in the Mole Ratio of O_2 /Alcohol at 400°C and b) Temperature on conversion of propan-2-ol.

The oxygen in the feed can generally have a dual function in the reaction viz: (i) to maintain the active form of the catalyst and (ii) to prevent any coke formation.

The oxidizing species in the system during oxidation may be the oxide ions of the catalyst or adsorbed oxygen. The gas phase oxygen could enhance the oxidation by a homogeneous reaction as well. If the catalyst ions are participating in the reaction, gas phase oxygen may merely replenish the anion-vacancies created by reduction of the catalyst surface.

The amount of acetone decreases with time even when there is oxygen in the feed (fig. 3). This decrease in activity may be due to the progressive reduction of the catalyst the oxygen in the feed being unable to simultaneously oxidize the reduced form or due to inhibition by products or due to the rate of oxidation of catalyst being slower than the reduction of the catalyst.

Fig. 3. Effect of time on conversion of propan-2-ol.

Carbon dioxide may be formed directly by combustion of alcohol (parallel) or by oxidation of acetone (consecutive) or by both paths (parallel and consecutive).

In the case of most catalysts with a high selectivity the products of complete oxidation are largely formed through sequential oxidation of the target product of partial oxidation i.e. reaction (2). This will have a strong effect on the selectivity of the catalyst. Reactions proceeding in parallel with the partial oxidation i.e. reaction 3 will be contributing only in a minor manner.

For these reasons, a high selectivity requires that the rate of oxidation of the alcohol to the partial oxidation product i.e. acetone must be high and the rate of further oxidation should be very low. The contribution of the consecutive reaction becomes especially important when the oxygen containing compound is very reactive.

The experiments performed in a reactor incorporating a large free volume showed that the reaction could not be explained solely in terms of gas-liquid (heterogeneous) reaction, but there may be some homogeneous reaction before and after the catalyst bed.

Many catalytic oxidation processes considered recently as purely heterogeneous appear to proceed by the heterogeneous-homogeneous mechanism⁹. Such are the oxidations of benzene over V₂O₅ catalyst¹⁰ and methane to formaldehyde¹¹. Daniel and Keulks¹² have demonstrated the initiation of the homogeneous oxidation of propene by oxygen containing reaction products formed on the surface of bismuth-molybdenum. The products of total oxidation were found to depend on the post-catalytic volume.

In order to find out whether the carbon dioxide formed is from the gas phase reaction or from the catalyst surface, the oxidation of alcohol was studied in the absence of a catalyst. The various products formed from the alcohol and the extent of conversion in the homogeneous and catalyzed oxidation processes must be compared in order to assess the activity of the catalyst.

Blank runs were performed in an empty glass reactor as well as one filled with glass chips of uniform size. First, various mole ratios of oxygen and alcohol were passed through the empty reactor. The conversion of alcohol to acetone was maximum at a mole ratio of oxygen to alcohol of 0.15. The conversion to acetone was 14%. The pyrolysis of the alcohol is negligible as shown in Fig. 4. The products are carbon dioxide, water and acetone. So, there is a significant interaction of oxygen with alcohol in a homogeneous reaction. The activity is maximum at 420° and further increase in temperature leads to the profound oxidation of the target product as shown in fig. 4. The total oxidation of alcohol, which can be seen by the decrease in the amount of unconverted alcohol with rise in temperature, is also taking place. Increase in oxygen pressure from 0.15 mole ratio to 0.18 mole ratio during the process first leads to total combustion of acetone that has formed already. Any further increase in oxygen-alcohol mole ratio cause profound oxidation of alcohol. The oxidation of acetone seems to be much more sensitive to the oxygen partial pressure than the oxidation of alcohol. This can be seen from the constant amount of unconverted alcohol during the two runs i.e. i) at 0.15 mole ratio of oxygen-alcohol and ii) at 0.18 mole ratio of oxygen-alcohol.

The reaction has also been studied in a reactor filled with various volumes of glass-chips of uniform size. The reduction of the volume of the reactor brings

Fig. 4. Effect of a) The variation in the mole ratio of O₂/Alcohol at 400°C and b) Temperature on the homogeneous conversion of propan-2-ol.

down the conversion of alcohol to very low values. The oxidation of alcohol studied in a reactor completely filled with glass-chips of uniform size showed that conversion of alcohol nearly equals the pyrolysis reaction at that temperature. So, we can say that the homogeneous reaction—the reaction in the empty reactor—is considerably more selective to acetone than the reaction in the reactor filled with glass-chips. In contrast to propan-2-ol, methanol undergoes no homogeneous reaction even after several hours at 460° if no catalyst is present¹³.

Acetone undergoes homogeneous oxidation more readily than does alcohol. This is clear from the difference in the amount of water found in the products during the oxidation of acetone and alcohol with the same oxygen pressure at 400°. Above 400° the oxidation of acetone becomes quite appreciable.

This type of blank runs with alcohol-oxygen mixtures is not sufficient to determine the importance of homogeneous processes during catalytic runs. The intermediates in catalytic oxidation of alcohol may be more reactive than the alcohol itself. Besides, some intermediates may act as initiators for homogeneous oxidation after the catalyst bed. The experimental test is to incorporate enough precatalytic volume and post-catalytic volume and compare the results with each other. For example, in the course of investigating the catalytic oxidation of propane to acrolein in a Bi-Mo-P-O catalyst¹⁴, it was shown that in a 'post-cat' space, acrolein is destroyed. Similar homogeneous reactions may occur in intergranular spaces of the catalyst bed¹⁰. This point has been generally overlooked by most

workers in the field of heterogeneous catalysis. The main consequence arising from the difference between the homogeneous and catalytic reaction is selectivity.

The oxidation of alcohol has been carried out by keeping the catalyst at either end of the reactor. Thus in one set enough post-catalytic volume is incorporated to allow the homogeneous and heterogeneously initiated homogeneous reaction. In the other set considerable pre-catalytic volume is provided for the homogeneous reaction before the catalytic reaction takes place.

It is found that formation of acetone depends on the position of the catalyst bed.

Acetone formed as a function of the position of the catalyst bed. The temperature of the catalyst bed was measured with a movable thermocouple to verify that the variation in reaction did not result from a variation of temperature at various positions in the furnace. The temperature variation which was not more than 3° cannot account for the variation in conversion.

TABLE—1

Time (min)	Temperature : 400°C			
	O ₂ /Alc. Mole ratio : 0.2	Case A : Catalyst at the entrance of the reactor	Case B : Catalyst at the middle of the reactor	Case C : Catalyst at the end of the reactor
5–10		52%	70%	30%
20–25		35%	58%	20%
40–45		28%	50%	18%

In case B, the formation of acetone is maximum. When oxygen and alcohol are admitted there will be a significant attack of oxygen on alcohol before they reach the catalyst. The oxygen pressure that is then present in the gas phase may preferentially oxidize the reduced catalyst than the acetone formed in the homogeneous reaction. This can partially explain why the activity is maintained at 70% in the case B. In the case C the acetone formed will be attacked by the oxygen as there is more precatalytic space than in the case B. In the case A, the activity is only due to catalytic reaction and there may be some influence of heterogeneously initiated homogeneous reaction which leads to oxidation of acetone. The position of the catalyst in the reactor determines partly its facility to get oxidized and in turn its ability to promote the heterogeneous reaction.

It is open to question whether the decomposition reaction

is an oxidative process or dehydrogenation with subsequent oxidation of hydrogen. It has been sugges-

ted that if there is any oxidative dehydrogenation of a hydrocarbon, hydrogen should be completely absent in the product. It is also required that hydrogen should not reduce these catalysts under the experimental conditions¹⁵.

The catalyst, subjected to pretreatment by H₂ at various intervals of time showed a decrease in catalytic activity for propan-2-ol decomposition.

TABLE—2 RESULTS ON CATALYSTS PRETREATED WITH HYDROGEN

Temperature : 400°	C. T. 1 sec
Catalyst	Percent Acetone/hr.
1 Fresh sample	50
2 Sample reduced 20 min.	60
3 Sample reduced 60 min.	48
4 Sample reduced 180 min.	40

For the fresh sample the initial catalytic activity corresponds to 50% conversion to acetone. This may involve excess surface oxygen¹⁶. In the catalyst, which was reduced with hydrogen for 20 minutes, on the assumption that all the adsorbed oxygen will be removed, the activity is due to only active metal-oxygen oxidizer groups. The increase in time of pretreatment of hydrogen gives a definite degree of reduction corresponding to stripping off several layers of oxygen. Hence the decrease in acetone formation with time of treatment with hydrogen.

An aged catalyst i.e. catalyst reduced with alcohol was treated with steam for several hours and then the activity for decomposition was checked. There was no change in activity. It shows that the catalyst could not decompose steam. The aged catalyst on use for n-hexane, cyclohexane and benzyl alcohol decomposition showed that it is a very poor dehydrogenation catalyst for benzyl alcohol and it is inactive for the other two substrates.

From all the above observations it can be concluded that the decomposition and oxidation of alcohol can take place in several ways as suggested below.

a) Hydrogen reduces the catalyst, so that decomposition reaction can take place as

In the process all the hydrogen need not get oxidized which is true as there is a small quantity of gas evolution during decomposition.

b) No propylene is found in the gaseous products and yet water is present in the liquid products. Further

the formation of acetone decreases with time inspite of the presence of oxygen in the feed. These would suggest that an oxyreductive mechanism may also be effective.

The oxidation reaction may show a complex character due to the occurrence of numerous simultaneous, consecutive and parallel reactions as shown below.

No carbon monoxide could be detected in the products by Orsat analysis using ammoniacal cuprous chloride solution. However, the influence of carbon monoxide – a possible product during catalytic oxidation – was checked; a) by pretreating the catalyst with CO before decomposition of alcohol, b) by introducing CO during oxidation of alcohol. The results are given in fig. 5. CO did not affect the conversion of alcohol. The qualitative test for carbon dioxide during the treatment of a fresh catalyst with CO showed that in the initial stages i.e. upto 5 min. CO₂ formation was observed and no CO₂ was formed after 5 minutes. The treatment of CO was made for 1 hr. and occasional checking for CO₂ has shown that there was no CO₂. This clearly shows that the Zn:Cr:Fe cannot oxidize CO with the lattice oxygen at 400°. The initial formation of CO₂ must be due to oxygen adsorbed on the catalyst in the process of preparing and calcining the specimens in air. In contrast to carbon monoxide, hydrogen pretreatment of the catalyst produces a definite degree of reduction.

Oxidation catalysts have been classified into two groups¹⁷ namely true oxidation catalysts and dehydrogenation catalysts. The oxidation catalysts (transition metal oxides) promote reactions like oxidation of CO to CO₂ and homomolecular isotopic exchange of oxygen by virtue of their ability to adsorb oxygen molecules and return them in an activated state. The dehydrogenation catalysts (especially molybdates) promote the oxidation of ammonia and methanol as these systems are capable of extracting atoms from the reacting molecules in the first elementary step of the oxidation reaction.

Fig. 5. Effect of products on the reaction.

The electrical conductivity of Zn:Cr:Fe does not change in the presence of oxygen at 400°. This shows that the catalyst is not chemisorbing oxygen.

On the basis of the various observations the Zn:Cr:Fe catalyst could be classified under the group of dehydrogenation catalysts.

The catalytic activity of the catalyst pretreated with CO₂ as well as the oxidation of alcohol in the presence of CO₂ (fig. 5) have shown that there is no change in activity. So, it can be very well said that CO₂ is not an inhibitor causing the decrease in dehydrogenation activity.

The reaction of secondary alcohols are particularly sensitive to retardation by water. Here, the presence of water during oxidation of the alcohol has made a small decrease in the formation of acetone (fig. 5).

The results support the hypothesis postulated by Haber¹⁸ viz., (a) in the partial oxidation process a good selectivity is exhibited only by those catalysts whose surface is completely free of adsorbed oxygen molecules or atoms and (b) partial oxidation takes place only with the participation of the lattice oxygen of the catalyst.

In this mild oxidation, all our results support the view that the oxidizing species is the oxide ion on the catalyst and gas-phase oxygen in the homogeneous reaction. Chemisorbed oxygen is ineffective.

A good partial oxidation catalyst must have (i) active sites on the surface which are capable of adsorbing the alcohol in a form enabling it to react by the oxyreductive mechanism; (ii) a crystal lattice or defects present in the anionic sublattice, enabling the oxide to permit the oxygen ions to diffuse rapidly through the lattice; (iii) sites on the surface which enable the already reduced catalyst to be rapidly reoxidized.

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